

POLITICAL SCIENCES

DIGITALISATION AND SECURITY IN THE FACE OF INCREASED GLOBAL RISKS

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Abstract

Digitalisation increases the speed and quality of information processing. The transition from mechanical to analogue to digital information transmission and processing devices is inevitable due to the advantages of the latter. These advantages are coupled with risks - information theft and manipulation are possible. The risks are particularly unacceptable in areas directly related to national security - military, energy, water supply, transport, etc. In the context of globalisation, disruption through cyber-attacks of extended production chains is painfully felt. That is why the US, EU, China and Russia are paying particular attention to cyber-security issues. Increased risks in some cases necessitate a return to less efficient but better protected information processing chains - analogue and even mechanical. The choice of a solution depends on weighing technological options against economic calculations, taking into account political considerations. In an environment of increased risk, the latter weighs heavily.

Keywords: information, digitalization, risks, security

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Introduction

In recent years, cybersecurity has become a mainstream topic in both the corporate world and at governmental level. Protecting information from theft and manipulation, capable of causing great damage to an individual, enterprise or country, has become a major concern. The misuse of information is made possible by its storage and transmission in binary code, so-called digitisation. The risks that this process entails make it necessary to consider its possible limits.

1. Methodology

Considering the possible limits of digitisation requires taking into account the three groups of factors that determine the implementation of any innovation: technological, economic and political. The first group provide answers to the question of whether a solution to a given problem is possible. The second group answers the question of whether a solution is justified from a cost perspective. The third group of factors decides whether an economically viable technical solution conflicts with societal needs and practices that have more than just financial dimension. The interaction between the three groups of factors is complex - the search for new technical solutions may arise out of economic necessity, but also for political reasons, including security. On the other hand, scientific and technical progress often offers new solutions whose economic and political implications have yet to be assessed by society. This paper presents the relationship between the three groups of factors in the case of digitisation and digital data protection.

2. Evolution of computing devices

Currently, digitization consists of processing information through computing devices operating in binary code (0-1). This method is fast, enables high quality, processes large information volumes, saves time and energy, optimizes management. Primary information in nature is transmitted by analog signal. The

processing is reduced to the conversion of the analogue signal into a digital one by electronic devices - switches of electric current (radio tubes, semiconductor elements).

The increasing demands on information processing go with the second wave of the scientific and technical revolution of the 19th – 20th century with the mastery of electricity and the introduction of the internal combustion engine. Their applications in transport and communications now exceeded the human brain's capacity to process incoming information quickly and correct. It is no coincidence that Norbert Wiener developed Cybernetics as science by creating a mathematical model apparatus for directing the fire of air defence systems - by 1939 the speed of a combat aircraft (400-500 km/h) was already too high for adequate defensive human reaction (Wiener, 1948).

Aids have been used since antiquity. The famous Antikythera mechanism is said to be the oldest known computing machine. Mechanical analog devices continue to be used today. They were even used in the first space missions, including the Globus mechanical computer, which was fitted to every manned Soviet and Russian Vostok, Voskhod and Soyuz spacecraft until 2002 (Siddiqi, 2003).

However, electricity makes it possible to make computing machines that meet the growing needs. During World War II, analog electronic computers were already being used for encryption and gunnery aids, as stated above. They operated with analog signals converted to continuous electrical signals controlled by electrical switches by changing the parameters of variable resistances, capacitances, and inductances. These computers are ideally suited for implementing automatic control over manufacturing processes as they instantaneously respond to various changes in input data. (Dorodnitsyn et al., 1989) They are therefore widely used in aviation and rocketry for real-time information

processing and subsequent formation of control signals in autopilots and various more complex automatic flight control systems or other specialized processes. One of their advantages, along with the speed of computation, is reliability - under disturbance conditions, machine availability is restored as soon as the disturbance disappears. Over time, however, their limitations in overall speed of operation become apparent. Amid the increasing volume of information, it remains low for purely physical reasons - the computations rely on transients in the reactive components, and are also limited by the bandwidth and load of the operational amplifiers. The nature of the analog signal puts obstacles in the way of reducing the size and power consumption of electronic devices. Nevertheless, their use in solving problems with lower accuracy requirements, for example in solving differential equations, is still justified today.

3. Nature and advantages of digitalization

In other areas, they have been displaced by digital computers working with data that is constantly changing over time. They record analog waveforms in a limited set of numbers, zeros and ones and process them that way. If analogue devices gave less information loss in the early days, over time techniques have been developed to detect and correct errors, remove interference from digital signals and improve quality. This breakthrough allowed the networking of individual computers, both internal (Intranet) and external (Internet), and the construction of large shared stores of information ("clouds"), as well as a common, much larger processing capacity.

An important advantage of digital technology is miniaturisation. Planar technology, developed in 1958, allows the reduction in size of electronic elements beyond their physical perception. In 2021, IBM announced the creation of a new two-nanometer chip accommodating about 333 million transistors per square millimeter.¹ Combined with the use of optical fibre for connectivity, entire information circuits are now physically reduced to just the size and power supply of the analogue receiver and digital-to-digital signal converter, with corresponding mirroring devices at the output. The example of the development of digital mobile telephones, which have rapidly displaced analogue ones, is relevant, notwithstanding the good quality of the latter. The comparison between the capabilities of the Apollo Guidance Computer (AGC), which controlled Apollo 11, and the iPhone XS Max phone shows even better the reduction in size and the increase in volume and speed of information processing. The phone

has 7 million times more RAM than the on-board computer and a 100,000 times faster processor. (Kendall, 2019) And sending humans to the moon is still the most complex technological operation in human history.

The volume and speed of information processing reached such a point that in May 1997 the Deep Blue computer defeated the world chess champion, Garry Kasparov, something that was thought to be impossible. But by the time of the 1997 match, the system's overall average computational speed was already 126 million positions per second, and the maximum sustained speed observed during the match was 330 million positions per second. (Kasparov, 2017) After 2010, the term "artificial intelligence" came into common use. It most often reflects attempts to optimize the computational process by replacing linear mathematical operations with parallel ones, adding feedback and hence the possibility of self-learning. Most successes have been achieved in the fields of logistics, medical diagnostics, machine learning, natural language understanding and translation, spectrometry, and virtual reality creation.

Adding in the advantages of copying - analogue communication copies are inferior to their originals, while digital copies are error-free and copies can be made indefinitely - one can see why the digitisation of the economy is sweeping across all fields and is accompanied by fundamental changes in technology, culture, operations and the principles for creating new products and services. It saves energy and raw materials, increases the reliability and speed of management processes, frees up manpower (which in the short term creates social problems) and allows new technological tasks to be solved, more complex even than sending men to the moon. According to the calculations of Russian scientists, e.g. the overall digitalization of agricultural production allows reducing the total costs by 23%, while the inefficient application of agribusiness tools ruins up to 40% of the harvest.²

That is why, to accelerate digitisation, the EU is providing €127 billion for digital-related reforms and investments in the 25 National Recovery and Sustainability Plans that have so far been endorsed by the Council. Member States have allocated on average 26% of their Recovery and Sustainability Mechanism (RSM) funds to digital transformation. The official target for the Union is 75% digitisation of the governance process by 2030. Progress in this direction has been uneven, as the figure shows. But it is inevitable.

¹ IBM Unveils World's First 2 Nanometer Chip Technology, Opening a New Frontier for Semiconductors, May 6, 2021, <https://newsroom.ibm.com/2021-05-06-IBM-Unveils-Worlds-First-2-Nanometer-Chip-Technology,-Opening-a-New-Frontier-for-Semiconductors>

² Ministry of Agriculture of the Chuvash Republic, The use of digital technologies in the agro-industrial complex significantly reduces the costs of farmers <https://agro.cap.ru/news/2018/03/16/primenenie-cifrovih-technologij-v-apk-znachiteljno-s>

Fig. 1: Digital Economy and Society Index, 2022

Source: European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/bg/ip_22_4560

4. Weaknesses and risks in digital systems

Fifty years ago, Alvin Toffler (Future Shock, 1970) pointed out an important feature of the economies of highly developed countries: information becomes the most important resource, but unlike tangible assets, it can be multiplied in time and place, yet retaining its value. Its misuse cannot always be detected and prevented, and current habits and legal frameworks are by no means suited to deal with this problem.

And the miniaturisation described above exacerbates the problem further, as the physical media associated with fibre and over-the-air networks make it even more difficult to fix and protect information. In addition, the characteristics of the digital signal allow it to be decoded and manipulated. If the analogue signal can only be jammed to the point of unusability, the digital signal can be transformed for misuse, and this first finds application for military purposes. (An example from the recently massively deployed unmanned aerial devices, the so-called 'drones': an analogue-controlled drone can be disabled by jamming the control signal, while a digitally controlled drone can be 'hijacked' and 'captured' by decoding and altering the control signal.)

Moreover, the creation of networks and shared information sets provide a very wide scope for abuse through the application of software programs, widely known as "viruses", with various tasks: stealing data, parasitizing on other people's memory and computing capacity, and worst of all, subjugating computers to external commands. Apart from this, the miniaturisation of digital devices allows them to embed features that the user does not suspect: suspicions that a person can be tracked by their personal phone or TV without noticing, or that their car can be locked by a command to the on-board computer, may have merit.

If for personal users malicious interference is capable of causing great trouble, interference with the infrastructure serving the public spheres can bring down the overall security architecture. And this is true not only for defense. The operation of power plants and electrical grids, of water supply networks, of transportation, of health care are already largely digitized in highly developed countries. At the highest political level, these risks are well understood and identified, together with possible countermeasures. These include

both the fight against/for the monopoly on the production of ever faster devices with ever higher capacities and the development of software for/against misuse. Both areas are summarised by the term "cyber security".

It becomes central in official documents of the UN, the US, China, Russia, the EU and other power centres. In a context of international tensions, questions are being raised about the sustainability of the microelectronics supply chain, and the formation of its own technology clusters. Achieving and maintaining technological sovereignty is becoming an imperative in international relations. The localisation of production aims at creating technological clusters. It can also lead to technological dependence of less developed countries on developed countries, which is also a non-military challenge to the cybersecurity of the former's critical infrastructure. Today, this is most evident in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies (Karasëv, Stefanović, 2022).

In the United States Presidential Policy Directive 21 (PPD-21) of 2013 deals with protection of digitized systems. According to the document, there are 16 categories of facilities vulnerable to attack, including communications systems, critical manufacturing facilities, dams, military-industrial facilities, emergency services, energy, financial services, food production and agriculture, government agencies, healthcare facilities, nuclear reactors, transportation systems, water and wastewater systems.

The EU has been working on the issue since 2004, when the Commission adopted a Communique on the protection of critical infrastructure sites in the fight against terrorism, including energy installations and networks; communications and information technology; financial institutions; healthcare; food production; water supply; transport; production, storage and transport of dangerous goods; and government structures. In Law No. 187-FZ of the Russian Federation, the list is similar, including the fuel and energy complex, nuclear power, defense, missile and space industries, mining, metallurgy, and chemical industries. China's approach to cyber security also prioritises it, relying more on state structures and less on the private sector in drafting regulations and specific countermeasures. The main difference between the Chinese approach and

the practices of the US, Russia and the EU is the distinctly proactive nature of the countermeasure: specially trained security personnel must be constantly involved in decision-making regarding the cybersecurity of information objects. (Karasëv, Stefanović, 2022)

China was the first country to impose comprehensive control over the Internet on its territory.

5. Ways to improve security

Globalisation facilitates the division of labour between countries and in the design and manufacture of microelectronics. The development of microchips is decoupled from their production, resulting in a total global semiconductor market volume of USD 555 billion in 2021, with 20% of all semiconductors being produced in Taiwan and 70% in East Asian countries overall. However, the technological monopoly in the chip market is held by the Dutch company ASML, which holds over 90% of the chip machine production through the lithography technique it has developed. Currently, it is the only manufacturer of the latest generation of chip-making machines using ultraviolet light (EUV). With its machines, 5-nanometre chips are being produced in series - the highest density of transistors per unit area, or the highest computing power ever achieved.

The company's monopoly explains the pressure that the US government has put on the Dutch and Taiwanese governments to stop sales to competitors and adversaries. China, e.g., is still two years behind in the production of 5-nanometer chips and 7-nanometer chips, and Russia plans to start fully autonomous production of 7-nanometer chips only by 2028. If the performance gap in information processing in other fields is not fatal, in armaments it could become decisive, especially in robotic systems controlled by artificial intelligence. (Digitisation is already determining the effectiveness of intelligence, aviation, artillery, even infantry combat.) Thus, the technological monopoly/oligopoly is becoming a major security concern. At the UN level, attempts to develop norms, rules and principles for responsible state behaviour and to create a global culture of cyber security and protection of critical information infrastructures (UN General Assembly Resolution 58/199) seem like a good wish. It is not clear what could stop the race to acquire and retain a technological monopoly.

The lag in production of increasingly powerful chips may provoke attempts to enhance security other than breaking the monopoly. The first is the use of electromagnetic weapons, developed in the 1950s and 1960s, which use a powerful electromagnetic pulse to knock out electronics at a distance of several tens of kilometers, like a lightning bolt. (An electromagnetic bomb was first used in a combat setting in 1990 during the Gulf War 1990-1991.) Standard semiconductors, especially microchips, are particularly vulnerable to such effects. Not only enemy weapons (tanks, artillery systems, etc.) but also the aforementioned civil infrastructure systems can be the object of attack in a conflict. An option for defence may be to return critical systems to analogue control, even with electronic devices with radio tubes where conditions permit - with the inevitable loss of capacity, increased size and power

consumption. It's all a matter of weighing the gains and losses of such technological regression. (In the former USSR, tank troops in the 1980s were also trained to operate by the archaic flagellar method precisely in view of the danger of using radio-electronic warfare.) In 2016, NASA announced that its Automaton Rover program for extreme environments would use a mechanical computer to operate in the harsh environmental conditions of Venus. (Sauder et al., 2016)

It should also be taken into account that digitisation is sometimes an end in itself and only aims at increasing the profits of producers through so-called "luxury inflation", i.e. increasing the price at the expense of additional facilities, amenities, etc. It is an axiomatic truth that perfect solutions are simple. E.g. the introduction of the on-board computer in cars 40 years after the beginning (1981) has still not convincingly proved its advantages: the higher initial price and the cost of repairs hardly manage to compensate for the savings made by digitising consumables. After the start of the war in Ukraine, Russia e.g. faced a shortage of chips. It is therefore trying to build up a self-sufficient, independent vehicle production without using digital control systems. The solution may prove acceptable to consumers. It should be made clear here that countries rich in raw materials and energy (not just Russia) are able to ignore the savings offered by digital devices in the name of the security afforded by being cut off from external suppliers and the ease of protection against disabling or externally controlling the computing devices that control military and civilian processes. The problems are mainly for resource and energy poor subjects of international relations such as the European Union.

Conclusion

Increased risks in some cases necessitate a return to less efficient but better protected information processing circuits - analog and even mechanical. The choice of a solution depends on weighing technological options against economic calculations, taking into account political considerations. In an environment of increased risk, the latter weighs heavily. The global crisis of 2008 unleashed conflicts of regional and global scope. Globalisation as a process to ensure peace through production and trade integration meets attempts to renationalise control over economies, the potential for conflict grows. Increased risks will certainly necessitate a rethinking of the limits of digitalisation - both in areas directly related to security and in areas where the benefits of digitalisation seem unproven.

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INSTITUTIONAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL PROVISION OF COMMUNICATIONS IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN UKRAINE IN THE CURRENT CONDITIONS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF REFORMS

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ІНСТИТУЦІЙНЕ ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ ДЕРЖАВНОЇ КОМУНІКАЦІЙНОЇ ПОЛІТИКИ В СУЧАСНИХ УМОВАХ РЕАЛІЗАЦІЇ РЕФОРМ

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Abstract

The article analyzes the domestic institutional and legal environment for the formation and implementation of the state communication policy, determines the state and problems of the formation of the institutional mechanism of communication management, outlines the prospects for its optimization in the conditions of the implementation of reforms regarding the openness and transparency of state authorities.

Анотація

У статті аналізується вітчизняне інституційно-правове середовище формування та реалізації державної комунікаційної політики, визначається стан та проблеми формування інституційного механізму управління комунікаціями, окреслюються перспективи його оптимізації в умовах впровадження реформ щодо відкритості і прозорості органів державної влади.

Keywords: communication, state communication policy, institutional and organizational support of the state communication policy, interaction with the public.

Ключові слова: комунікація, державна комунікаційна політика, інституційно-організаційне забезпечення комунікаційної політики держави, взаємодія з громадськістю.

Постановка проблеми. Аналіз комунікаційної політики України та її ефективності на сьогоднішній день, рівня довіри громадян до органів державного управління та підтримки ними соціально-економічних процесів і реформ та соціальних змін тощо свідчить про недостатню інституційну спроможність держави щодо такої багатовекторної діяльності. Забезпечення злагодженої взаємодії органів державної влади, місцевого самоврядування та інститутів громадянського суспільства щодо цілепокладання, прогнозування, планування та програмування, прозорості та відкритості їх діяльності, залучення громадян до процесу державотворення, підтримки міжнародної спільноти та належного використання державних комунікаційних можливостей стає актуальним питанням.

Теоретико-методологічні основи інституційного забезпечення державної комунікаційної політики є предметом достатньої кількості досліджень вітчизняних та зарубіжних фахівців в галузі державно-управлінських наук. Дослідження окремих проблем формування ефективних інституційних механізмів державної комунікаційної політики містяться у роботах А. Баровської (вивчення європейського досвіду інституційного забезпечення державної комунікаційної політики), А. Халецької (дослідження інституційного забезпечення взаємодії органів державної влади та громадянського суспільства на трьох рівнях: інституційному, функціональному та законодавчому), П. Манжолі (обґрунтування необхідності посилення інституційної спроможності громадських рад при органах державної